

Modular Multi-Level Converter Model for the Analysis, the Design and the Optimization of DC Power Systems Involving Superconducting Power Cables Cooled by Liquid Hydrogen

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Abstract—DC power transmission technologies have achieved significant advancements, gaining widespread adoption within modern electrical systems. The use of superconducting cables in Magnesium Diboride (MgB_2) cooled by liquid hydrogen (LH2) could drastically increase the performance of DC grids, enabling higher power transport capacity and extending transmission distance, while reducing energy loss and land occupation. Today, the transport of DC electrical energy is enabled through modular multi-level converters (MMCs) capable of effectively controlling currents, voltages and power flow. Designing an optimal DC power system, along with appropriate superconducting cable design and protection apparatus, needs accurate, yet simplified, models of the converters. This study presents simplified models that apply during the fault, able to adapt to any pre-fault scenario without a need to implement complex control systems. The developed model can be easily integrated, along with a model of a superconducting MgB_2 cable, in EMT power system simulators for analysing their mutual interaction during faults and for optimizing the cable design and its protection system.

Index Terms—Grid models, liquid hydrogen, modular multi-level converter, MgB_2 cables.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE need of flexible and efficient power transmission technologies has made modular multilevel converters (MMCs) increasingly pivotal in modern High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) systems [1], [2], [3], [4]. Particularly important is

Received 28 September 2024; revised 24 January 2025; accepted 12 February 2025. Date of publication 18 February 2025; date of current version 12 March 2025. This work was supported in part by the European Union—Next Generation EU under the framework of the NEST (Network 4 Energy Sustainable Transition) SPOKE 7 and/or ECOSISTER SPOKE 4, PNRR - M4C2 - I1.3, and in part by the SCARLET project funded by European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant 101075602. (*Corresponding author: E. Guerra.*)

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Color versions of one or more figures in this article are available at <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASC.2025.3542742>.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TASC.2025.3542742

their use in multiterminal DC grids based on integrating power superconducting (SC) cables [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], which exhibit remarkably high rating, low losses and reduced voltage drop that can enhance the overall performance of the power systems. Cost-effective cables technology based on MgB_2 superconductor is recently emerging as key enabler for high-efficiency energy systems employing hybrid lines transporting both electric power and hydrogen produced by large power plants [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], like emerging offshore wind farms. Nevertheless, the complexity related with modelling SC cables while taking into account the complex behaviour of Modular Multilevel Converters (MMC) poses significant challenges from the simulation point of view [11], [31], [24]. Thus, new modelling approaches, both for cables and converters, need to be developed to accurately investigate the interaction of the cable with the power systems both in normal and in fault conditions.

To address these challenges, the development of simplified circuit models for MMCs to be combined with the circuit model of the MgB_2 cable is addressed in this paper. These models can bridge the gap between theoretical analysis and practical implementation, allowing for more accessible and effective computational analysis. By focusing on the fundamental characteristics of MMCs — including their modular structure, non-linear behaviour, and interaction with superconducting cables — these simplified models can significantly facilitate the analysis of the behaviour of the designed SC cable during faults. The paper is organised as follows: the reference case study, consisting of the grid connection of a 2 GW off-shore wind farm through MgB_2 power cable and MMC converters stations at both the sending and the receiving ends is first presented in Section II, explaining in detail the system components and the MgB_2 cable model. In Section III, the simplified model of the MMC is described and validated through comparison with existing MMC models including full detail of the control. In Section IV the results obtained by applying the simplified MMC model to the reference case study are showed and discussed.

II. SELECTED CASE STUDY: GRID CONNECTION OF 2 GW OFFSHORE WIND FARM

The same case study proposed in [7] involving a 2 GW/ ± 100 kV DC link for the grid connection of off-shore wind power is selected for this work. The key difference introduced

TABLE I
MgB₂ CABLE PARAMETERS

	Unit	Value
Rated current	kA	10
Rated voltage	kV	100
Rated power	GW	1
Rated Temperature	K	20
Line length	km	100

Fig. 1. Electric system considered for the analysis.

Fig. 2. Circuit model of a wind farm used in the grid model.

in this paper is the use of an MgB₂ cable cooled with liquid hydrogen (LH₂) instead of a High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) cable. The current and voltage levels of the transport cables are set equal as in [7] and reported in Table I. The grid model including the behaviour of the SC cable and the MMC is implemented in MATLAB/Simulink environment. The details of the system are as follows

A. System Components

The grid analysed consists of a symmetrical HVDC monopole connection of ± 100 kV between an offshore wind farm and the onshore AC grid. The onshore AC/DC converter stations are composed of three clusters of wind generators with 667 MW total power each, as shown in Fig. 1. The equivalent DC model of the wind farm cluster depicted in Fig. 2 has been adopted to simulate the generator behaviour during faults. This model ensures that the fault current remains at the rated value, reproducing the “ceiling effect” of AC/AC converters connected to the generators [11]. On the onshore side, the DC link is connected to the AC grid through three identical MMC units with 700 MVA rating connected in parallel. The AC grid is assumed to be ideal, while the effect of the transformers’ impedance is taken into account in the model. All system data are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II
GRID AND MMC PARAMETERS

Grid parameters	Unit	Value
AC voltage grid side	kV	400
DC voltage	kV	± 100
Transformer apparent power	MVA	700
Transformer ratio (grid)	kV	110/400
Transformer leakage inductance (grid)		15 %
MMC parameters		
Number of converters units		3
Arm inductance of each MMC	mH	16 / 0.15 pu
Number of sub-modules per arm		100
SM capacitance	mF	20
Rated SM capacitor voltage	kV	2
Rated capacity of the converters units	MVA	700

Fig. 3. Layout of the considered MgB₂ cable.

B. Cable Design and Model

In order to evaluate the viability of employing MgB₂ cable technology for the reference case study, a preliminary design of the cable system was carried out. For the cable core (including the former and the MgB₂ layers), the ± 275 kV/10 kA MgB₂ cable design proposed in [19] has been assumed as a starting point. The thickness of the electrical insulation (PPLP), has been adjusted compared to [19] to consider the voltage level of this case study, imposing a maximum electric field of 20 kV/mm. The layout of the considered cable is shown in Fig. 3. The electro-thermal model of the cable follows the approach described in [11], [19], [20], considering LH₂ as coolant. The focus of the paper was to combine the simplified MMC model with the cable model discussed in the next sections to explore the resilience of the selected cable layout with respect to different fault conditions via numerical simulation, in order to check the cable design and to highlight the need for possible optimization.

III. MMC MODEL

MMC technology represents the state of the art for modern Multi-Terminal HVDC systems [1], [2], [3], [4]. Its modular architecture allows for easy adaptation of the converter design to meet the desired voltage and current ratings, while maintaining high reliability and output voltage quality [1]. However, due to the large number of non-linear and reactive components inside the converter (IGBTs, diodes, capacitors and inductors), the computational burden of these converters can be quite high, especially in complex electrical grid systems [2], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29]. In [30], various modelling strategies are presented, classified from Type 1 to Type 7, each tailored to specific types of analysis. The model proposed in this work belongs to Type 6 (Simplified Average Value Models). It is valid

Fig. 4. SM chain during IGBT blocking. (a) Detailed model. (b) Equivalent simplified model.

only to analyse fault conditions on the DC or AC grid and refers to an MMC with half-bridge sub-modules (SMs).

A. Simplifying Assumptions

During DC fault, the MMC converter operates under two working conditions: the first occurs when the fault arises and the converter has not yet been blocked, and the second occurs when the blocking of the converter is triggered and all the IGBTs are opened. The blocking of the converter typically occurs when a certain threshold value of current is surpassed. A threshold value of twice the rated DC current is assumed in this paper for the blocking of the converter, as in [31], [32], [33]. During IGBTs' blocking phase, the whole chain of submodules in one of the six arms of the converter can be represented by means of the equivalent simplified model of Fig. 4, and the corresponding parameters can be calculated using (1)–(3).

$$C_{eq} = \frac{C_{SM}}{N_{SM}} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{ON,eq} = N_{SM}V_{ON} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{ON,eq} = N_{SM}R_{ON} \quad (3)$$

where C_{SM} is the SM capacitance, N_{SM} is the number of SM in each arm of the MMC and V_{ON} and R_{ON} are the internal parameters of each diode. In Fig. 4 L_{arm} is the inductance added in each arm of the converter for limiting the fault current rise rate, and R_{arm} is the corresponding resistance. The full model of the three-phase MMC when IGBTs are blocked is shown in Fig. 5, whereby the whole chain of modules is represented by the equivalent simplified model of Fig. 4. To adopt this model, the initial condition for the current in the inductors and the voltage of the capacitors must be assessed, as it discussed next. Finally, it is noted that during the non-blocking phase of the converter (that is, from fault occurrence to the moment the current reaches the threshold of twice the rated level) the series of the SMs can be modelled as a voltage source with $0.5 \cdot V_{DC}$ voltage. This assumption is justified by the fact that the usual control strategy of the converter during normal operation, which maintains the

Fig. 5. DC and AC current repartition on MMC's arms.

balance of the voltage of the capacitors and inserts/disconnects the modules so to create a total average voltage $0.5 \cdot V_{DC}$ in each arm, is applied in this phase too. We have verified, through comparison with the detailed MMC models developed in the frame of the SCARLET project [11], that negligible error is obtained with this assumption.

B. Initial Conditions Calculations

The initial values (at the fault occurrence) for the currents and voltages in the inductors and capacitors can be derived by assuming that, when the fault occurs, the system is operating in balanced AC steady state conditions. Under these circumstances, the RMS value of the AC currents can be calculated based on the active and reactive power delivered by the MMC to the AC grid, as well as the RMS value of the pole-to-pole voltage of the grid. Similarly, the current on the DC side can be obtained from the DC power (neglecting the losses, it coincides with the AC active power) and the DC bus voltage. Under these assumptions, the pre-fault conditions of the DC current (i_{dc}) and AC currents (i_{ga} , i_{gb} , i_{gc} , where a, b and c refer to the three phases) are distributed across the converter's arms as shown in Fig. 5. Thus, the arm currents can be calculated using (4) and (5).

$$i_{u,j} = \frac{i_{dc}}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{2} I_{g,RMS} \sin(\omega t - \varphi - (j-1)\frac{2}{3}\pi)}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$i_{l,j} = \frac{i_{dc}}{3} - \frac{\sqrt{2} I_{g,RMS} \sin(\omega t - \varphi - (j-1)\frac{2}{3}\pi)}{2} \quad (5)$$

where $I_{g,RMS}$ is the rms value of the AC current and φ is the lag angle between phase current and voltage, deduced from AC active and reactive power settings, and j is the phase index ($j = 1, 2, 3$). Regarding the capacitor voltage, it varies during normal converter operation due to the current flowing through it when the SM is active. However, the MMC's lower-level control loop manages the charge and discharge of the SM capacitors, keeping them balanced at a value equal to V_{DC}/N_{SM} , with a typical ripple below 10% [29]. Based on this assumption, the voltage of C_{eq} at the initial instant can be assumed equal to V_{DC} .

Fig. 6. Case study adopted for the validation of the simplified MMC model.

TABLE III
PARAMETERS OF THE REFERENCE SYSTEM FOR THE MMC MODEL VALIDATION

Transformer	Symbol	Unit	Value
Windings connection			Yg - y
Transformer resistance	R_1 pu, R_2 pu	pu	0.0015
Transformer inductance	L_1 pu, L_2 pu	pu	0.06
Converter			
Number of SM	N_{SM}		36
SM Capacitance	C_{SM}	mF	1.758
Arm Inductance	L_{arm}	mH	52.95
Arm Resistance	R_{arm}	m Ω	166.3
System active power	P_{nom}	GW	1
System reactive power	Q_{nom}	MVar	250
Grid			
Bus DC voltage	V_{DC}	kV	640
Pole to Pole RMS voltage (primary)	V_{AC1}	kV	400
Pole to Pole RMS voltage (secondary)	V_{AC2}	kV	333
Short circuit power of 400 kV AC grid	P_{SC}	GVA	20
X/R ratio of 400 kV AC grid	X/R		7
Pre-charge resistor		Ω	400
Fault			
Resistance		Ω	1

C. MMC Model Validation

The simplified MMC model has been compared with the so-called *aggregated model* of the Hitachi MMC converter available in MATLAB/Simulink environment [34]. The reference case of Fig. 6, involving a back-to-back configuration of two MMC converters, was considered for the purpose of the validation. The parameters of the system are listed in Table III. In the pre-fault condition, MMC1 delivers 1 GW of active power and 250 MVAR of reactive power to AC Grid 1, while MMC2 absorbs 1 GW of active power and no reactive power from AC Grid 2. The fault current profiles (I_{DC2}) resulting from both the complete and the simplified models are compared in Fig. 7. The calculated mean relative error is 0.43%, allowing the proposed model to be considered validated.

Fig. 7. Comparison of I_{DC2} obtained with the reference Hitachi aggregated model [34] and the proposed simplified MMC model during fault.

TABLE IV
PARAMETERS OF THE REFERENCE SYSTEM FOR THE MMC MODEL VALIDATION

Generators	Symbol	Unit	Value
Nominal voltage	V_{DC}	kV	200
Clamping voltage	V_{CL}	kV	220
Current source	I_0'	kA	3.33
AC Circuit breakers			
Opening time		ms	60
Resistance in closed state		m Ω	1
Conductance in open state		μ S	1
Fault			
Resistance		Ω	1
Distance fault 1		km	75
Distance fault 2		km	99

IV. RESULTS

This section reports the results in terms of current and temperature repartition in the cable main layers, obtained by simulating the behaviour of the grid depicted in Fig. 1. Two pole-to-pole fault scenarios were simulated, with the fault occurring at different distances from the wind farm along the transmission line. In particular, the first scenario assumes a pole-to-pole fault occurring along the SC line, 75 km away from the wind farm, while in the second scenario the same fault occurs at 99 km from the wind farm. Results are calculated by combining the MMC model described in Section III with the electrothermal circuit model of the designed MgB₂ cable, obtained through the method introduced in [11]. Throughout all this section, I_{DC1} denotes the current circulating in the wind farm side of the circuit whereas I_{DC2} denotes the current circulating in the grid side, as depicted in Fig. 1. A solid bond scheme of the cable, considering that the copper shield of both the monopole cables is grounded at both the ends of the DC transmission link, is assumed for the simulations [11]. It is also assumed that the ACCBs open after 60 ms (vertical dashed lines will represent this instant in the following figures). The main characteristics of the modelled fault, the ACCBs, and the wind farm model are listed in Table IV; the “generators” parameters refer to the structure depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 9. Currents (a) and temperatures (b) profiles of the cable's layers and total cable's core resistance (c) during Fault scenario 1 on the grid side section of the cable.

Fig. 11. Currents (a) and temperatures (b) profiles of the cable's layers and total cable's core resistance (c) layers during Fault scenario 2.

A. Fault Scenario 1

Fig. 8 shows the profiles of the currents I_{DC1} and I_{DC2} after the fault occurring at 75 km. It is noted that a fault current continues to flow within the DC circuit even after the opening of ACCBs. This is due to the freewheeling path offered by the diodes of the half bridge SM. Fault current through the 75 km long section of the MgB_2 cable (I_{DC1}) fluctuates close to the rated value due to the current ceiling effect of the generators. Fig. 9 illustrates the detail of current and temperature profiles in the SC cable layers, and the total core resistance (obtained as the parallel equivalent of copper former and MgB_2 layer resistances) in the 25 km cable section between the fault and the AC grid. The transition of the MgB_2 layer occurs about 18 ms after the fault, as observed from the cable's core resistance profile in Fig. 9(c). At the same time, Fig. 9(a) shows that the current in the MgB_2 layer reaches about 18 kA. The consequent increase of the temperature of the MgB_2 layer is shown in Fig. 9(b). After the opening of the ACCBs, the temperatures of the copper and MgB_2 layers continue to rise, beyond the critical temperature, because the current on the DC side of the MMC converter is not sharply interrupted but decreases slowly according to the decay law of the loop RL formed by the two monopoles. During this phase, the shield's temperature quickly decreases due to thermal exchange with the coolant. The temperatures of the former and MgB_2 layers decrease very slowly due to the poor thermal conductivity and the relatively high thickness of the electrical insulation. While decreasing, they also tend to slowly homogenize due to heat exchange through steady hydrogen flow present among them [20]. It is pointed out that the designed

cable is not fault transparent since the temperature reached by the MgB_2 is too high for the cable to resume normal operation at the fault clearance.

B. Fault Scenario 2

As shown in Fig. 10, in the first instants of the simulation the fault current through the 1 km cable section (I_{DC2}) rise rapidly until 20 kA (2 pu of the rated cable current). The converter is then blocked and all the IGBTs are opened. From Fig. 11, it can be observed that the transition of the MgB_2 layer occurs almost instantly, as evidenced by the increase in the cable's core resistance and the temperatures of the layers. After the opening of the ACCBs, the current in the copper and MgB_2 layers decreases much more rapidly compared to Fault scenario 1, due to the lower inductance of the considered cable section. It is also important to note that, although the opening of the ACCBs does not interrupt the DC fault, it still helps limiting the overheating of the cable core. Similarly to the previous fault scenario, the reached temperatures are too high to re-establish working operations. However, in both simulated scenarios, the calculated overtemperature is not sufficient to cause irreversible damage to the cable layers, assuring fault tolerant MgB_2 cable designs. System's and/or cable's designs need to be reviewed if a fault transparent (and not only tolerant) design has to be achieved.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an approach for a simplified MMC modelling, with a reduced number of components and avoiding the need of a complex control system, adaptable to different SM architectures. The proposed approach is applied to a grid case study implemented in MATLAB/Simulink, involving a 2 GW offshore wind power farm connected to the land grid through a LH₂-cooled MgB₂ cable appositely designed. Two fault scenarios were analysed, which allowed to confirm the fault tolerance of the designed cable.

Future work will involve the evaluation of the effect of possible optimization actions of the MgB₂ cable design, such as increasing the wires critical current or use more resistive former and evaluating other cable architectures. The impact of different system layouts for the same cable design, and system redesign including the introduction of superconducting fault current limiters (SFCL) and the adoption of Full Bridge Submodules within the MMC, will also be explored by means of the developed model.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, nor can the European Union be held responsible for them.

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